

A Physics-Informed 3D U-Net for Ultrasound Acoustic Phase Analysis–Based Tracking of Magnetic Microrobots

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I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

In recent years, untethered microrobots (MRs) have attracted increasing attention due to their great potential to improve minimally invasive medicine [1]. Their small scale allows them to travel deep into the vasculature and access narrow anatomical regions, enabling localized interventions such as targeted drug delivery, biopsy, and microsurgery. Their clinical translation, however, is critically conditioned by the availability of a real-time imaging modality capable of tracking them inside the human body to support controlled navigation. Ultrasound (US) imaging stands as the best candidate because it is safe, low-cost, and offers high temporal resolution. However, standard B-mode tracking struggles in highly echogenic tissues, where low contrast and speckle artifacts mask the MR signature.

Ultrasound Acoustic Phase Analysis (US-APA) [2], [3], [4] has emerged as an effective alternative. By processing the instantaneous phase of the complex Radio-Frequency (RF) signal, US-APA isolates the sub-wavelength motion of the MR from the static background, enabling contrast-enhanced localization in tissue. However, classical implementations rely on computationally demanding Fourier analysis and filtering. While effective in controlled in vitro environments such as phantoms, these analytical methods are fragile under realistic conditions, in which tissue micro-motion, probe coupling, and electronic noise inject phase perturbations that are hard to distinguish from the actual MR signal. Furthermore, narrow-band filters assume that the MR vibrates at a constant, perfectly known frequency. In practice, non-linear physical interactions between the MR, its actuation source, and the surrounding viscous tissue often shift or broaden the vibration spectrum, degrading the filter’s accuracy.

Deep learning has rapidly emerged as a powerful tool for MR localization in US imaging [5], [6], [7]. However, essentially all of these approaches operate on B-mode images, which are subjected to logarithmic compression, and numerous filtering and gain settings (such as TGC, gain and dynamic range). As a consequence, B-mode-based networks inherit a structural dependency on the imaging parameters of the specific hardware and operator, which limits their robustness across acquisitions. Moreover, as the development of US-APA demonstrated, the most discriminative information about MR motion does not lie in the envelope but in the phase of the raw RF signal. In this domain, sub-wavelength displacements produce coherent modulations that the B-mode discards. Motivated by these considerations, we investigate

whether the deterministic core of US-APA can be replaced by a learned spatio-temporal detector operating directly on the raw phase cineloop, without bandpass filters or heavy Fourier analysis. This approach merges the representational power of deep learning with the physical richness of the phase domain, and is intrinsically invariant to the operator-tunable parameters that produces the B-mode image. The implementation of this approach is prevented by the lack of labeled real data: ground-truth MR positions are not available. In this paper we address this gap through a physics-based synthetic data generator used to train a 3D U-Net.

II. METHODS

Experimental data were acquired with an open-architecture ArtUS research platform (Teleded, Lithuania) equipped with a high-frequency L15-7H40 linear probe operating at 10 MHz center frequency and 90 frames per second (FPS). A spherical NdFeB microrobot (MR) (1 mm diameter) was actuated inside a tissue-mimicking phantom through a multi-coil navigation platform (OctoMag, Magnebotix), producing oscillating magnetic fields to induce in-place vibrations at controllable frequencies (1 to 20 Hz).

While the experimental setup provides the realistic acoustic environment, the lack of large-scale ground-truth MR coordinates prevents direct supervised learning on real RF data. To overcome this limitation, training is performed on a physics-based synthetic data generator. Real RF backgrounds acquired on agar and tissue-mimicking phantoms are Hilbert-transformed and stored as complex volumes that carry speckle statistics, tissue micro-motion, and probe artifacts. A simulated vibrating MR is then superimposed. The MR acoustic footprint is modeled as an anisotropic Gaussian envelope (with axial and lateral resolutions of 0.037 mm and 0.150 mm, respectively). Its axial motion is modeled as a standard sinusoid, $d(t) = A \sin(2\pi ft)$, which induces a proportional phase shift defined as $\Delta\varphi(t) = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} d(t)$.

To process this complex dataset, we propose a 3D U-Net designed to localize the MR by processing a short temporal sequence (32 frames) of phase data into a single 2D probability heatmap. The network follows a classic encoder-decoder structure [8]. The encoder progressively extracts abstract spatio-temporal features through consecutive 3D convolutional blocks (going from 8 to 64 channels), while the symmetric decoder reconstructs a prediction map. By processing space (x, y) and time (t) jointly with 3D convolutions, the network naturally learns the MR vibration signature. To track fast vibrations without information loss, we use spatial-only pooling ($1 \times 2 \times 2$ kernels) that preserves

the full temporal resolution across all layers. To avoid the artificial 2π jumps in raw angular data, we split the input phase into sine and cosine channels, providing the network with a smooth, continuous signal.

To ensure robust generalization, we randomize the simulation parameters across the system operating conditions. MR diameters vary from 0.5 to 1.2 mm, actuation frequencies span 1 to 20 Hz, and target SNRs are uniformly sampled between 0 and 10 dB. Furthermore, rather than keeping vibration amplitudes strictly below the phase wrapping limit ($\lambda/4$), we deliberately allow them to cross this threshold. This exposes the network to temporal aliasing during training, teaching it to recognize and localize wrapped phase signatures. We further degrade the signal with up to 0.5 rad of additive phase noise to emulate realistic tissue and electronic perturbations. Finally the model is trained for 100 epochs (with early stopping) using the Adam optimizer ($lr = 1 \times 10^{-4}$).

III. RESULTS

The network was evaluated qualitatively on a set of independent vibration recordings spanning 1–20 Hz actuation frequencies. By combining the OctoMag control data with the corresponding B-mode images, we establish a solid ground truth for every recording. When the trained network is applied to real recordings, the predicted MR centroid consistently overlaps the MR position visible in the B-mode image, and the output confidence map exhibits a compact, well-localized peak at the MR site, with a negligible residual response over the background (Fig. 1). This behavior is preserved across the full set of tested acquisitions. Beyond standard localization, our data-driven approach provides significant practical advantages over classical analytical pipelines. First, it tracks the microrobot across the full 1–20 Hz range without requiring manual filter adjustments. Second, it is highly resilient to non-ideal locomotion. While rigid band-pass filters fail when physical interactions modify the vibration spectrum, our network is robust to these irregularities. Third, wrap-aware training allows the model to track the robot even when high-amplitude vibrations exceed the $\lambda/4$ physical limit, a regime where classical methods completely break down due to phase aliasing. Furthermore, by replacing heavy signal processing steps like FFTs with a single feed-forward pass, the network lowers computational load, becoming feasible for real-time closed-loop robotic control.

IV. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES AND CONCLUSIONS

We presented a physics-informed 3D U-Net that aims to improve US-APA tracking as a learned spatio-temporal detection problem. By training only on synthetic vibrating targets superimposed on real tissue RF backgrounds, our network eliminates the reliance on rigid, computationally expensive Fourier analysis. Future work will focus on integration into a closed-loop architecture in which the US probe is mounted on a robotic arm, as well as extending the validation to more complex locomotion modes, such as rolling MRs, helicoidal propulsion and biological swimmers.

Fig. 1. Representative tracking performance of the 3D U-Net. (Left) The standard B-mode US image, where the MR is difficult to distinguish from the highly echogenic tissue background. The network predicted location is marked with a green cross. (Right) The corresponding 2D spatial confidence heatmap generated by the network.

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